

Supplementary material

Article: Feeding habits influence species habitat associations at the landscape scale in a diverse clade of Neotropical fishes

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Content: Appendix S1, Tables S1-S8, Figure S1.

Appendix S1. Serrasalminae Phylogeny Construction:

We used the recent phylogenomic tree from Kolmann et al., (2021) to generate a phylogenetic framework to account for shared ancestry among species. Kolmann et al., (2021) used exon capture to generate a phylogeny of serrasalmids from 951 exons. The taxon sampling covers 63 of the currently recognized 100 serrasalmid species with representatives from all recognized serrasalmid genera. The exon probe set they used contains several exons that are legacy markers traditionally used in resolving fish phylogenetics (Arcila et al., 2017). To increase taxon sampling, we utilized six legacy markers sequenced by Kolmann et al., (2021) (COI, ENC1, FICD, IRBP, SREB2, and VCPIP) that have also been used to resolve fish phylogenetic relationships. We obtained additional sequences from GenBank for COI and SREB2 that have previously been used in resolving serrasalmid relationships (Thompson et al., 2014; Machado et al., 2018). Additionally, we added a marker not included in the exon dataset of Kolmann et al., (2021), PTR, which had previously been used for serrasalmid phylogenetics (Thompson et al., 2014). Two species, *Utiaritchthys sennaebregai* (SRX7670167) and *Serrasalmus hollandi* (SRX7670146), only have sequence data on the NCBI Sequence Read Archive from a recent ultraconserved elements (UCEs) study of serrasalmids (Mateussi et al., 2020). To add these species into our

phylogeny, raw sequence reads were trimmed with trimmomatic v0.36 (Bolger et al., 2014) to remove adapters and low-quality reads. We then extracted COI by assembling mitochondrial genomes from UCE sequence reads using MitoFinder (Allio et al., 2020), assembling against the mitogenomes of *Myloplus rubripinnis* (MH358336) and *Pygocentrus nattereri* (AP012000), respectively. Sequences for each of the seven markers were aligned using MAFFT (Kato and Standley, 2013) and concatenated for a final 5,340 bp dataset of 73 serrasalmid species. The final alignment was partitioned by gene and codon position. ModelFinder (Kalyaanamoorthy et al., 2017) was used to merge partitions and select the best-fit model for each partition. We then performed a constrained tree search using IQ-TREE 2 (Minh et al., 2020), constraining the topology to follow the one recovered by Kolmann et al., (2021) while resolving the phylogenetic relationships of taxa that were not included in their tree. To convert the phylogeny into an ultrametric tree, we used the congruify.phylo function in the R package geiger (Eastman et al., 2013; Pennell et al. 2014) to generate secondary calibrations from the divergence time estimates in Kolmann et al., (2021). Using these secondary calibrations, the tree was time-calibrated using treePL (Smith and O'Meara, 2012) with the optimal smoothing parameter found via cross-validation.

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Table S1. List of species included in the study, number of occurrences and feeding guild classification.

Species	Number of occurrences	Feeding guild
Acnodon_normani	260	Herbivore
Acnodon_oligacanthus	1	Herbivore
Acnodon_senai	5	Herbivore
Catopriion_mento	332	Fin_Scale Feeder
Colossoma_macropomum	501	Frugivore
Metynnis_altidorsalis	20	Planktivore
Metynnis_argenteus	103	Planktivore
Metynnis_fasciatus	3	Herbivore
Metynnis_guaporensis	85	Herbivore
Metynnis_hypsanchen	296	Planktivore
Metynnis_lippincottianus	92	Herbivore
Metynnis_longipinnis	8	Herbivore
Metynnis_luna	155	Planktivore
Metynnis_maculatus	174	Herbivore
Mylesinus_paraschomburgkii	84	Herbivore
Mylesinus_paucisquamatus	2	Herbivore
Myloplus_arnoldi	66	Herbivore
Myloplus_asterias	238	Herbivore
Myleus_micans	4	Herbivore
Myleus_pacu	98	Herbivore
Prosomyleus_rhomboidalis	67	Planktivore
Myloplus_schomburgkii	232	Herbivore
Myleus_setiger	274	Herbivore
Paramyloplus_ternetzi	17	Herbivore
Myloplus_tiete	2	Herbivore
Myloplus_torquatus	170	Herbivore
Myloplus_rubripinnis	457	Herbivore
Mylossoma_aureum	789	Frugivore
Mylossoma_duriventre	1253	Frugivore
Ossubtus_xinguense	45	Herbivore
Piaractus_brachypomus	389	Frugivore
Piaractus_mesopotamicus	4	Frugivore
Serrasalmus_calmoni	115	Piscivore
Serrasalmus_striolatus	256	Herbivore
Pygocentrus_cariba	11	Piscivore
Pygocentrus_nattereri	1187	Piscivore
Pygocentrus_piraya	17	Fin_Scale Feeder
Pygopristis_denticulata	146	Frugivore
Serrasalmus_altispinis	122	Piscivore
Serrasalmus_altuvei	60	Piscivore
Serrasalmus_brandtii	1	Piscivore
Serrasalmus_compressus	249	Piscivore
Serrasalmus_eigenmanni	331	Piscivore

Serrasalmus_elongatus	616	Fin_Scale Feeder
Serrasalmus_gibbus	13	Piscivore
Serrasalmus_gouldingi	213	Piscivore
Serrasalmus_hollandi	334	Piscivore
Serrasalmus_humeralis	117	Piscivore
Serrasalmus_irritans	10	Piscivore
Serrasalmus_maculatus	400	Piscivore
Serrasalmus_manueli	166	Piscivore
Serrasalmus_marginatus	58	Piscivore
Serrasalmus_medinai	36	Piscivore
Serrasalmus_rhombeus	2341	Piscivore
Serrasalmus_spilopleura	521	Piscivore
Tometes_ancylorhynchus	9	Herbivore
Tometes_kranponhah	13	Herbivore
Tometes_makue	16	Herbivore
Tometes_trilobatus	5	Herbivore
Utiaritchthys_longidorsalis	19	Herbivore
Utiaritchthys_sennaebregai	59	Herbivore
Total	13667	-

Table S2. Dietary items included into functional feeding guild classification of serrasalmid species.

Food items	Feeding guild
Fruits (including seeds)	Frugivore
Podostemaceae	Herbivore
Leaves	
Flowers	
Periphyton	
Zooplankton	Planktivore
Phytoplankton	
Fish	Piscivore
Scales	Fin & scale feeder
Fins	

Table S3. Quartiles and the corresponding feeding specialization degree that was used to classify serrasalmid species ranging from highly specialized to generalist and from highly frugivorous to non-frugivorous. NA: non-applicable.

Quartiles	Specialization level	Frugivory level
>75%	High	High
50-75%	Mid-high	Mid-high
25-50%	Mid-low	Mid-low
<25%	Low	Low
0%	NA	None

Table S4. Results from homogeneity of variance assumption testing through Levene test.

Model	Levene statistic	P value
Flood_ext_Mean.10km ~ Feeding guilds	0.8051	0.5271
Flood_ext_Mean.5km ~ Feeding guilds	0.6891	0.6026
Flood_ext_Mean.25km ~ Feeding guilds	0.7289	0.576
Shannon_300m ~ Feeding guilds	2.317	0.06832
Shannon_5km ~ Feeding guilds	2.5995	0.04572 *
Shannon_25km ~ Feeding guilds	1.3316	0.2696
Flood_duration_300m ~ Feeding guilds	1.041	0.3943
Flood_duration_5km ~ Feeding guilds	0.3793	0.8225
Flood_duration_25km ~ Feeding guilds	0.4998	0.736

Results of Floodplain extent quartile 1

Table S5. PGLS results for Floodplain extent using the quartile 1 as response variable. Feeding guild abbreviations: Her: Herbivore, Pis: Piscivore, Frug: Frugivore, Pla: Planktivore, FScF: Fin and Scale feeder. Bold values represent $p < 0.05$.

<i>Predictors</i>	Floodplain Extent 5km Q1			Floodplain Extent 10km Q1			Floodplain Extent 25km Q1		
	<i>Estimates</i>	<i>CI</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>Estimates</i>	<i>CI</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>Estimates</i>	<i>CI</i>	<i>p</i>
(Intercept)	0.23	-0.42 – 0.88	0.492	0.17	-0.49 – 0.83	0.616	0.11	-0.53 – 0.75	0.742
Feeding_guild_L [Pis]	0.26	0.07 – 0.45	0.009	0.27	0.08 – 0.46	0.007	0.26	0.08 – 0.45	0.008
Feeding_guild_L [Frug]	0.32	0.13 – 0.50	0.001	0.36	0.17 – 0.54	<0.001	0.32	0.14 – 0.50	0.001
Feeding_guild_L [Pla]	-0.18	-0.36 – -0.00	0.051	-0.18	-0.36 – 0.00	0.056	-0.15	-0.33 – 0.02	0.091
Feeding_guild_L [FScF]	0.22	-0.03 – 0.46	0.094	0.25	-0.00 – 0.50	0.057	0.18	-0.06 – 0.43	0.151
Observations	61			61			61		
AIC	13.463			15.458			11.919		

Table S6. Pseudo- R^2 values for all the models calculated by comparing the log-likelihood of the full (actual) and reduced (intercept only) models.

Models	R² lik
Flood_ext_Mean.5km	0.509
Flood_ext_Mean.10km	0.539
Flood_ext_Mean.25km	0.585
Shannon.av.point.300m	0.245
Shannon.av.point.5km	0.386
Shannon.av.point.25km	0.563
Flood_duration_300m	0.342
Flood_duration_5km	0.039
Flood_duration_25km	0.060

Level of frugivory as predictor

Table S7. Results of PGLS for the response variable floodplain extent and frugivory level as predictor at the scales of 5km, 10km and 25km. Levels of frugivory abbreviations: LowF: Low frugivore, Mid-HighF: Mid-High frugivore, Mid-LowF: Mid-Low frugivore, NonF: Non frugivore. High frugivore is the reference frugivory level.

<i>Predictors</i>	Floodplain Extent 5km			Floodplain Extent 10km			Floodplain Extent 25km		
	<i>Estimates</i>	<i>CI</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>Estimates</i>	<i>CI</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>Estimates</i>	<i>CI</i>	<i>p</i>
(Intercept)	0.47	-0.21 – 1.15	0.184	0.42	-0.35 – 1.18	0.294	0.34	-0.41 – 1.08	0.379
Frug.Scale [LowF]	0.02	-0.23 – 0.26	0.902	-0.00	-0.28 – 0.27	0.980	-0.03	-0.30 – 0.24	0.839
Frug.Scale [Mid-HighF]	0.12	-0.14 – 0.38	0.377	0.11	-0.18 – 0.41	0.460	0.11	-0.18 – 0.39	0.470
Frug.Scale [Mid-lowF]	-0.15	-0.41 – 0.10	0.245	-0.20	-0.49 – 0.09	0.185	-0.20	-0.49 – 0.08	0.161
Frug.Scale [NonF]	-0.02	-0.26 – 0.23	0.887	-0.02	-0.30 – 0.25	0.863	-0.02	-0.29 – 0.24	0.856
Observations	61			61			61		
AIC	14.131			28.892			24.488		

Table S8. Results of PGLS for the response variable landscape heterogeneity and frugivory level as predictor at the scales of 300m, 5km and 25km. Levels of frugivory abbreviations follow

Table S1. High frugivore is the reference frugivory level. Bold values represent $p < 0.05$.

<i>Predictors</i>	Shannon av point 300 m			Shannon av point 5 km			Shannon av point 25 km		
	<i>Estimates</i>	<i>CI</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>Estimates</i>	<i>CI</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>Estimates</i>	<i>CI</i>	<i>p</i>
(Intercept)	0.97	-0.81 – 2.74	0.291	1.71	-0.04 – 3.46	0.060	1.45	-0.23 – 3.14	0.097
Frug.Scale [LowF]	0.22	-0.42 – 0.86	0.504	-0.09	-0.72 – 0.55	0.792	-0.21	-0.82 – 0.40	0.505
Frug.Scale [Mid-HighF]	0.50	-0.19 – 1.18	0.159	-0.13	-0.80 – 0.55	0.710	-0.17	-0.82 – 0.48	0.620
Frug.Scale [Mid-lowF]	-0.04	-0.72 – 0.63	0.897	-0.61	-1.27 – 0.05	0.077	-0.69	-1.33 – -0.05	0.039
Frug.Scale [NonF]	-0.07	-0.71 – 0.57	0.835	-0.17	-0.80 – 0.46	0.599	-0.21	-0.81 – 0.40	0.500
Observations	61			61			61		
AIC	131.159			129.157			124.715		

Figure S1. Estimated marginal means and the 95% confidence intervals per feeding guild of the fish family Serrasalminidae at three spatial scales in the Amazon River basin. a) Floodplain extent (proportion), b) Landscape heterogeneity (Shannon Index), and c) Flood duration (months). Feeding guild abbreviations: Her: Herbivore, Pis: Piscivore, Frug: Frugivore, Pla: Planktivore, FScF: Fin and Scale feeder. Letters above the bars indicate significant differences based on P values generated by Tukey HSD corrected pairwise comparisons per Phylogenetic Generalized Least Squares model. Feeding guilds with different letters are significantly different at alpha level of 0.05.